

ECHO

Cancer Mission Hubs

**Positioning the future EU network of
NCMHs in the European cancer landscape**

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Abbreviations

AC	Associated Countries
EBCP	Europe's Beating Cancer Plan
EC	European Commission
EU network	European network
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
MoC	Mission on Cancer
MS	Member States
NCMH	National Cancer Mission Hub
NCMH-like structure	National Cancer Mission Hub-like structure
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organisations
WP	Work Package

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1 Introduction

ECHO S (Establishing of Cancer Mission Hubs: Networks and Synergies) is set up to support the implementation of the European Mission on Cancer (MoC) in Member States (MS) and Associated Countries (AC). The aim is to support Member States (MS) and Associated Countries (AC) with the capacity to create National Cancer Missions Hubs (NCMHs). These NCMHs will play a major role in mobilising and involving relevant national, regional, and local stakeholders in cancer related initiatives, and increase awareness of the available funding opportunities.

ECHO S will develop guidelines, toolkits, and models for the efficient implementation of NCMHs, facilitate the mobilisation of stakeholders and the creation of synergies across the European cancer research and policy landscape.

Furthermore, ECHO S will set the foundations for the creation of a European Network of the NCMHs with the ambition to create a formal platform of knowledge sharing and support to the Cancer mission that will continue fostering collaborative research, policy alignment and stakeholder engagement efforts beyond the initial life span of the Mission on Cancer (2027). The ambition is to create a strong and cohesive network, aligned with the Mission on Cancer and Europe's Beating Cancer Plan.

To achieve this, ECHO S has set the following general objectives:

1. To promote the creation of National Cancer Mission Hubs in MS/AC
2. To establish a network of support to advance Cancer Mission across Europe
3. To create synergies for the implementation of the Cancer Mission with other European initiatives towards a "Cancer in all" approach
4. To create the foundations for a European network of NCMHs by developing a business continuity and operations model framework

Within ECHO S, work package (WP) 5 is leading the work towards the setup of an EU network of NCMHs. The work includes the definition of scope of the EU network, development of the governance and finance frameworks, and business models, and building a strategic roadmap for a sustainable European Network of NCMHs.

The following document presents the work done in task 5.1, specifically focusing on defining the scope of the EU network of NCMHs and its positioning within the EU cancer landscape.

2 Methodology

To develop the scope of a future EU network of NCMHs, and position it within the current EU cancer landscape, multiple steps were implemented. First, a scanning exercise was carried out to identify different active EU level actors within the cancer landscape. This exercise was intended to provide an overview of existing networks and organisations that could have a complementary or competing role to the potential future EU network of NCMHs. The aim of this exercise enabled the identification of possible links, collaborations and avoid duplication/overlap of activities of different networks. Therefore, the focus of the scanning was on organisations that play a role in bringing together multiple stakeholders, disseminating information on EU projects relevant to the cancer field, and/or participating in EU projects tackling cancer.

A broad web-based search was implemented starting from a general search through the official European Commission (EC) websites for relevant associations and networks. Thereafter, a snowballing approach provided a more focused search by checking the partner lists of different relevant EU and international projects. Furthermore, the partners of WP5.1 were consulted and asked to provide additional relevant European associations or organisations that were not yet included in the list.

To narrow down the list of relevant EU level actors, the scanning focused on the following inclusion criteria for organisations that:

1. Operate with an EU focus (national and global organisations without EU focus were excluded).
2. Cover the whole disease spectrum (i.e. not focusing on a specific cancer subtype)
3. Active and participating or promoting participation in EU (co-) funding opportunities (this includes informing their members about the opportunities, supporting their members to create consortiums, apply for calls)

A list of relevant organisations was prepared, and information was extracted from their websites regarding their scope and activities.

The second step of this task included the developing of potential activities that the future EU network of NCMHs could provide in its role of supporting the NCMHs. The initial list was developed based on similar activities from already existing network, as well as discussions with the partners of task 5.1.

To validate the list of activities a survey was developed and sent to all ECHO S partners. The respondents were asked to rank the list of activities taking into consideration their feasibility. The survey also included questions regarding possible constrains, needs and expectations with regards to the implementation of a future EU network of NCMHs. The survey was launched through Limesurvey and was accessible from February 12th - 23rd, 2024.

Furthermore, in-depth interviews were organised in April 2024 with three identified existing NCMH-like structures, who have answered the survey and indicated that they were available for further interviews. The discussions were guided by a semi-structure interview guide (annex II). The topics discussed included the NCMHs activities, challenges faced by the NCMH-like structures, as well as potential pitfalls that need to be considered and mitigated when establishing an EU network for the NCMHs.

Finally, with the purpose of triangulation, the 5.1 task leads had the opportunity to discuss with ECHO S partners and representatives of NCMH-like structures who attended the task 2.3 knowledge exchange programme in Brussels (April 2024). The workshop focused on discussing and refining the general objectives of the EU network of NCMHs and co-developing the mission and vision statements.

3 Results

The following section elaborates on the results of the above-mentioned steps.

3.1 Scanning relevant actors in the EU cancer network landscape

Table 1 provides the list of relevant actors that could have a complementary or competing role to the potential future EU network of NCMHs. Following the inclusion criteria the following list of organisations and associations were analysed for information on their websites regarding their scope and activities.

Table 1. List of organisations and associations as relevant actors in the EU cancer network landscape

Name and acronym	Scope	Actively promotes participation in EU calls	Dissemination and outreach	Activities
<p>Association of European Cancer Leagues (ECL)</p>	<p>A non-profit, pan-European umbrella organisation of national and regional cancer societies, i.e. patient organisations. Located in Brussels, ECL provides an exclusive platform for members to collaborate with their international peers, primarily in the areas of cancer prevention, tobacco control, access to medicines and patient support, and creates opportunities to advocate for these issues at the EU level.</p> <p>ECL's vision is: A Europe free of cancers. ECL's mission is: To advocate for improved cancer control and care in Europe through facilitating collaboration between cancer leagues and influencing EU and pan-European policies.</p>	<p>Participates in EU funded projects and Joint Actions</p> <p>Furthermore, ECL advocates for collaborations to influence policy</p>	<p>Has a platform for outreach and communication between cancer societies</p>	<p>Main activities include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Patient support working group -ECL task force for access to medicines - Information at EU level (cancer prevention, tobacco control, MEPs against cancer) and events <p>No trainings identified</p>
<p>European Association for Cancer Research (EACR)</p>	<p>A registered charity is a professional membership association and global community for those working and studying in cancer research, with more than 12,000 members worldwide.</p> <p>EACR mission is: The advancement of cancer research for the public benefit: from basic research to prevention, treatment, and care.</p>	<p>Provide a variety of services and funding opportunities to their community of members.</p>	<p>Core activity is to facilitate communication and collaboration among members</p>	<p>Provide services and organise highly rated webinars, scientific to conferences and an annual congress for their members.</p> <p>Also includes funding of postdoctoral fellowships, travel fellowships/grants, different awards, research development grants.</p>

<p>International Association of Cancer Registries (IACR)</p>	<p>A professional society, mandated as part of the WHO, which is dedicated to fostering the aims and activities of cancer registries worldwide.</p> <p>The Association was created to foster the exchange of information between cancer registries internationally, so improving quality of data and comparability between registries.</p>	<p>It is an international organisation with a participation in EU projects and recently launched a joint research call for cervical cancer screening/diagnosis and management</p>		<p>Provides and facilitates <u>learning and capacity-building opportunities</u></p>
<p>The European Network of Cancer Registries (ENCR)</p>	<p>A European network that promotes collaboration between cancer registries, defines data collection standards, provides training for cancer registry personnel and regularly disseminates information on cancer incidence and mortality in Europe.</p>	<p>Was established as a results of and EU funded project and partners with EU funded projects.</p> <p>Collaborated with JRC to set up a standardised and comparable database for monitoring cancer incidence and mortality in the European Union and to provide regular information on the burden of cancer in Europe.</p>	<p>Promotes collaboration between cancer registries, defines data collection standards.</p>	<p>Provides training for cancer registry personnel and regularly disseminates information on cancer incidence and mortality in Europe.</p>
<p>European Cancer Organisation (ECO)</p>	<p>ECO is a not-for-profit federation of member organisations working in cancer at a European level, bringing together oncology professionals and patients, advocate for positive change and be the united voice of the European cancer community, and facilitate collaboration and consensus towards tangible and impactful policy improvement.</p>	<p>Participates and coordinates EU projects.</p>	<p>Focusing on creating and developing relationships between different relevant stakeholders (for example relationships between European institutions and the European cancer care community).</p>	<p>Accreditation Council of Oncology in Europe (ACOE) provides accreditation to Continuing Medical Education (CME) providers</p> <p>Organises roundtables, organises <u>networks on different topics</u>.</p>
<p>European Organisation for Research and</p>	<p>EORTC is an independent, non-governmental, non-profit cancer research Organisation. Its mission is to coordinate and conduct international translational and clinical research to</p>	<p>EORTC participated in <u>numerous projects funded</u> by the EC in various cancer</p>	<p>Focus on treatment development and connection to industry (bringing robust datasets to</p>	<p>Of the activities provided:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Clinical trials -Infrastructure projects -Quality assurance

<p>Treatment of Cancer (EORTC)</p>	<p>improve the standard of cancer treatment for patients.</p> <p>EORTC also helps develop new drugs and approaches in partnership with the pharmaceutical industry and in patients' best interests.</p>	<p>and clinical research-related fields.</p>	<p>doctors and patients for therapeutic improvement.)</p>	<p>-Public policy -Young & early career investigator (clinical and translational cancer research)</p> <p>-Education & training</p>
<p>Organisation of European Cancer Institutes (OECI)</p>	<p>OECI is a non-governmental Organisation presently comprising 123 Members, which include some (self-declared) European Comprehensive Cancer Centres.</p> <p>The OECI aim is to accelerate the application of multidisciplinary personalised care approaches to reduce mortality and to guarantee an equitable access to care to all cancer patients and supporting parallel initiatives outside the EU and in other continents.</p>	<p>Participated in and coordinates projects funded by the EC.</p>	<p>Consists of members from different European institutions that are active in the area of cancer.</p>	<p>OECI has working groups, some of which focus on education and training.</p>
<p>European Cancer Patient Coalition (ECPC)</p>	<p>A large European non-profit cancer patients' association. Conducting internal consultations with Board Members and reviewing patient advocacy group strategies and best practices, we develop a final strategy to increase the impact of the organisation and establish long-term aspirations. The main objective is to firmly establish ourselves as the main voice of cancer patients in Europe and focus on activities that ensure patients play a leading role in the development of healthcare programmes in Europe.</p> <p>We also aim to strengthen organisations' capacity-building and increase the connections between us and our members. Through advocacy activities, fundraising and campaigns, we offer a unique doorway to a vast array of opportunities at a European level, utilising established connections</p>	<p>Through advocacy activities, fundraising and campaigns, we offer a unique doorway to a vast array of opportunities at a European level.</p> <p>Participates in multiple EU projects.</p>	<p>Outreach focusing more on different representative patient groups.</p> <p>Does not seem to be research focused.</p>	<p>Toolbox with educational materials and e-modules on a range of topics/ platforms/ resources.</p>

	and channels and reaching audiences through Member States.			
European Society for Medical Oncology (ESMO)	ESMO's core mission is to improve the quality of cancer care, including prevention and diagnosis all the way to palliative care and patient follow-up. It aims to educate doctors, cancer patients and the general public on the best practices and latest advances in oncology, and to promote equal access to optimal cancer care for all patients.	ESMO provides information on EU calls and how to apply.	Newsroom with press and media hub, daily reported oncology news and society updates.	ESMO organises meetings, congresses, virtual plenaries and courses. Courses for medical students and other career development options.
European Haematology association (EHA)	The EHA association brings together doctors (hematologists), researchers (PhD or otherwise), patients (and advocacy groups), geneticists, nurses, and more mainly across Europe, including non-EU member states. EHA has a global network and collaborates internationally with medical associations, National Societies, and many more organisations.	EHA provides its own grants Part of its advocacy priorities is support for hematology research by informing on EU funding and research policies.	EHA has an open access journal (HemaSphere) and includes lobbying to strengthen hematology's voice in Europe.	The activities of EHA include the organisation of an annual congress, provide and an educational program based on the European Hematology Curriculum.
European School of Oncology (ESO)	The European School of Oncology is an independently funded non-profit organisation providing education and training in the field of cancer	ESO is actively participating in several EU funded projects that are helping to implement Europe's Beating Cancer Plan and the EU Cancer Mission (INTERACT-EUROPE; CCI4EU).	ESO collaborates with other European and International organisations working on cancer, and launched two of the main breast and prostate cancer patient organisations in Europe.	ESO provides postgraduate and fellowship programs. Created an online platform E-ESO providing open access quality education. Organises policy forums in collaboration with The Lancet Oncology.
All.Can	All.Can is an international multi-stakeholder not-for-profit organisation working to improve the efficiency of cancer care by focusing on what matters to patients.	All.Can collaborates with European organisations and different initiatives funded by EU (e.g. IPAAC) in the cancer field.	Organises multi-stakeholders national initiatives, and highlight best practices in cancer care. Build and leverage partnerships and the	Gathers examples of best practice in cancer care from around the world to create a learning community around efficient practices. Involved in research and publications of peer-

			creation of visual resources on the importance of efficiency in cancer care.	reviewed papers and policy briefs.
The European Society for Radiotherapy and Oncology (ESTRO)	ESTRO as a society that aims to foster radiotherapy in all its aspects by setting standards in education and practice, facilitating research, stimulating exchange of scientific knowledge and promoting collaboration in radiotherapy in Europe and beyond as well as with other professions involved in cancer treatment.	ESTRO collaborates with several partners in the oncology field, and participates in EU funded projects .	ESTRO has a newsroom section where they disseminate in multiple communication methods such as publication and newsletters. ESTRO is also involved in many advocacy activities.	ESTRO provides on demand courses, and organises regular courses, workshops and congresses.
European Society for Paediatric Oncology (SIOPE)	A pan-European organisation representing all professionals working in the field of childhood cancers. SIOPE's mission is to ensure the best possible care and outcome for all children and adolescents with cancer in Europe. To achieve this goal, SIOPE addresses the main challenges faced by European paediatric oncology professionals through a multidisciplinary and pan-European perspective.	Participates and collaborates with EU funded projects .	Publications and newsletters and other resource links available.	SIOPE supports researchers in dealing with the regulatory aspects of clinical trials' initiation and acts as a point of reference to facilitate partnerships and information exchange among disease-specific clinical trial groups. Develops standards of care for children
Network for Rare Cancer (EURACAN)	EURACAN is a virtual network connecting highly specialised cancer centres across Europe. EURACAN also includes Associated Partners, which are European/ international scientific societies, national networks and patient organisations/advocates. The mission of EURACAN is to improve diagnosis, treatment management, knowledge, research and communication for all patients with rare adult solid cancers.	Participates and makes use of EU (co)-funding.	Publications and newsletters and organises different events.	EURACAN's activities focus on helping health professionals as well as patients. Develops clinical guidelines. Offers different educational possibilities for clinicians and healthcare professionals.

3.2 Survey

The survey was launched on February 12th, 2024, and was sent to all ECHO S partners. From the 30 MS/AC contacted, 21 MS/AC (32 entities) submitted a complete answer, representing a response rate of 70%.

As part of the survey, respondents were asked about challenges faced by their NCMH-like structure. This question was only asked to those respondents who answered that they are representative of the NCMH-like structures in their countries. Of the 32 respondents, 24 indicated that they participate/coordinate a NCMH-like structure. The following points represent a summary the current challenges reported by NCMH-like structures that an EU network could address:

- Developing governance model and ensuring a sustainable funding structure for the NCMH.
- Identifying and convincing the right and relevant institutions to collaborate as the NCMH.
- Implementing effective communication and engagement strategies tailored to specific stakeholder groups or communities.
- Difficulties to navigate the vast amount of (co)funding EU opportunities at a time.
- GDPR related challenges in information sharing.
- Difficulties retaining expertise and human resources.

Next, all respondents were asked what their needs and expectations of the future EU network of NCMHs are. The following list summarises the results indicating that the EU network should:

- Serve as an umbrella organisation bringing together all NCMHs, ensuring alignment of scope and activities in each MS/AC.
- Develop and be responsible for criteria setting and monitoring the NCMHs.
- Act as a formal platform to promote and facilitate sharing knowledge/expertise and best practices (inc. regular calls, topical meetings, informal chats between NCMHs).
- Inform and disseminated information regarding ongoing and upcoming events, calls, initiatives to mitigate redundancy and duplication in EU funded projects, and act as a 'one-stop shop' (sharing results and information between projects).

- Serve as a point of contact for interaction between NCMHs and supranational EU institutions, leading to EU-wide coordination and alignment, and to faster implementation of policies on cancer.
- Foster collaborative research including translational research and innovation, building strong and functional collaboration between MS/AC.
- Cooperate with other joint initiatives and explore EU and non-EU (co-) funding opportunities, e.g., by establishing close contacts and exchange with current EU-Health related funds and programmes.
- Develop and provide tools, methods and training to members on specific relevant topics for the optimal performance of NCMHs
- Facilitate the set-up of stakeholders and citizen engagement events and the continuous communication with stakeholders and citizens (including patient organisations) by NCMHs.

Outlined in table 2 are possible activities that the EU network of the NCMHs could perform. These activities were initially developed by the task leads based on the scanning of networks in the field (table 1), and discussion with partners from ECHO S task 5.1.

All respondents were asked to comment on the list and rank the activities in accordance with importance. Table 2 displays the activities ranked from the highest importance to the lowest by the survey respondents.

Table 2. List of possible activities of the future EU network of NCMHs

Activity	Description
1. Support the set-up of NCMHs in MS/AC	Next to training relevant for NCMHs, the EU network can provide the expertise for countries still in the process of setting up NCMHs.
2. Organise relevant trainings and workshops*	Provide capacity building specific to the NCMHs that are set up in the MS. The training or workshops will focus on topics such as: knowledge translation from research results into policy, training on change management and organisational readiness, and stakeholder engagement skills building workshops.

3. Facilitate the collaboration of NCMHs with other EU initiatives such as EBCP related projects*	Encouraging collaboration between the EU network (as representing the NCMHs) and other EU initiatives. To ensure objectives are aligned and facilitate synergies between different initiatives. This may also include providing funding to the NCMHs through open calls on specific topics for Cancer Mission.
4. Following- up of the NCMHs	Developing monitoring and evaluation standards or specific KPIs for the functioning of the NCMHs to ensure successful functioning of the NCMHs.
5. Serve as a contact point between the EC and the NCMHs	Depending on the final network governance structure, the EU network may serve as a representative to the NCMHs in relevant meetings or boards on behalf of the NCMHs. Thus, take the role of being the official voice of the NCMHs for topics such as development of EU policy.
6. Publication of white papers, policy reports, opinion papers	Publication of white papers, policy reports, opinion papers on behalf of NCMHs.

* both activities 2 and 3 marked with (*) were ranked equally important.

3.4 In-depth interviews

For the in-depth interviews, experts were selected based on the answers from 5.1 to ensure a variety of NCMH-like structures were included. Seven experts from three different countries were interviewed. The experts varied in their expertise and professional background, including institute director, head of departments, program managers, and researchers.

The interviews included some introductory questions to understand the background and functioning of the NCMH-like structure that was participating in the interview. Thereafter, discussions were guided by a semi-structure interview guide (see annex II) and covered topics such as current challenges within the NCMH-like structure that a future EU network of NCMH could support with, expectations and needs from a future EU network of NCMHs.

The main themes that were raised from the interviews are summarised below:

- Interviewees mentioned that establishing an EU network of NCMHs could serve as contact point between the EC and the NCMHs to improve communication between these entities. This theme emerged repetitively during the in-depths interviews indicating that it's a gap that can be addressed by such an EU network.

- An important activity of the EU network is providing Knowledge exchange and capacity building. These were indicated to be particularly relevant in the phase of setting-up the NCMH. This could include, but is not limited to, exchange of experiences and encouraging discussions between mature NCMH structures and structures that are being setup. The capacity building can then be maintained with a focus on relevant topics depending on the needs of the NCMHs.
- Interviewees indicated that future EU network of NCMHs could serve as a point of contact between EC and projects on cancer research and care, and possibly engage in cancer-related advocacy activities (see point 6 in table 2).
- Interviewees stressed the need for a governance that is flexible to support the different models of NCMHs.
- Ensuring that the NCMHs are supported, it was suggested that the EU network develops KPIs or agrees on standards which can then be used by the NCMHs to monitor their activities. These could be used to identify gaps and remaining needs.

Furthermore, to ensure sustainability is considered while developing the EU network in ECHO S WP5, the interviewees were asked to provide any points for consideration for the establishment of the network. These are important for the follow up within ECHO S tasks 5.2 and task 5.3 (for the governance and sustainability of the EU network). The following aspects were mentioned:

- How to attract MS/AC to partake in the activities of the EU network as paying members, considering that membership fee might be needed for sustaining the functioning the EU network. This may be difficult for some, especially smaller MS/AC.
- Develop the right governance structure for the EU network, considering that NCMH include many national stakeholders, which could pose a challenge in deciding who should partake in the network activities and how.
- With changes in leadership at national level they may impact whether the MS/AC remain members in the EU network. As such, it is important for the EU network to communicate a clear added value and benefit for the MS/AC to join.

3.5 Workshop

In general, the ambition of the EU network of the NCMHs is to create a formal platform of knowledge sharing and support to the NCMHs within MS/AC. This network will encourage and ensure that research collaborations, policy alignment, and stakeholder engagement efforts are continued beyond the initial life span of the Mission on Cancer (2027). This will build on the strong and cohesive network that will be fostered during the ECHO S project.

Based on the in-person workshop that took place in Brussels on April 16th, 2024, a working definition of the mission and vision of an EU network of NCMHs was co-developed. The suggested vision for the EU network of NCMHs is: “Breaking through cancer together- at all ages, at all stages”. The suggested mission statement of the EU network of NCMHs is: “Ensuring and supporting the collaboration for fundamental and translational cancer research, in line with the Mission on Cancer, and supporting evidence-based decision-making”.

4 Conclusion

This document presents a comprehensive overview of the scope and activities of a future EU network of NCMHs. The scope was defined by combining an understanding of the challenges, expectations of NCMH-like structures and the scanning of EU cancer network landscape. This activity-based approach allowed to appropriately address the needs of existing NCMH-like structures and future NCMHs and valorise the network for such structures.

Overall, respondents expressed enthusiasm towards having an EU network of NCMHs that support the cancer research landscape in Europe. However, they also expressed concerns regarding the duplication of efforts and encouraged leveraging ongoing task forces. Therefore, it is important to ensure that the purpose of the future EU network of NCMHs is not to repeat or duplicate the work done within the NCMHs, or the identified EU networks and organisations. Rather, the EU network will answer to the needs of the NCMHs and fill in the gaps, focusing on supporting the implementation of the Mission on Cancer within the MS/AC.

The activities developed and validated within this task present an initial list based on the needs and expectations of the ECHO S partners, who are working on the development of the NCMHs and participate in NCMH-like structure in their respective countries. These activities may be further discussed once the EU network and its governance is established, and adapted in accordance with the needs of the NCMHs. Similarly, the working definitions of the mission and vision, and the impact of the EU network of NCMHs on health, society and economy will be further defined once the business-continuity framework and strategic roadmap are completed.

Annex I

Survey 5.1 questions

1. Name
2. Country
3. Email
4. Do you represent a NCMH or an NCMH like structure in your country(?)
 - 3.1 If the answer is yes
 - 3.1.1 What are the challenges you are experiencing in your NCMH/NCMH like structure that you think an EU network can support?
 - 3.1.2 What are other needs you have from an EU network?
 - 3.2 If answered no,
 - 3.2.1 Are you aware of any existing structure?
 - 3.2.2 Could you provide a contact of the existing structure?
5. As a formal platform of knowledge sharing and encouraging collaborations, what are your expectations from an EU network connecting NCMHs? Please elaborate.
6. The following table provides a set of activities that the EU network may provide. Please rank the following in accordance with most important activity (1) to least important to (6).

Activity/service	Explanation	Rank
1. Training and workshops	Provide capacity building specific to the NCMH that are set up in the MS. The training or workshops will focus on the topics such as: knowledge translation from research results into policy, training on change management and organisational readiness, stakeholder engagement skills building workshop. *This topics may change depending on the models develop in ECHO S WP2 for the NCMH.	

2. Support the set-up of NCMHs in MS/AC	Next to training relevant for NCMHs, the EU network can provide the expertise for countries still in the process of setting up NCMHs.	
3. Monitoring the NCMHs	Developing monitoring and evaluation standards or specific KPIs for the functioning of the NCMHs to ensure successful functioning of the NCMHs.	
4. Facilitate the collaboration of NCMHs with other EU projects such as EBCP related projects	Encouraging collaboration between the EU network (as representing the NCMHs) and other EU initiatives. To ensure objectives are aligned and facilitate synergies between different initiatives. This may also include providing funding to the NCMHs through open calls on specific topics for Cancer Mission.	
5. Server as a contact point between the EC and the NCMHs	Depending on the final network governance structure, the EU network may serve as a representative to the NCMHs in relevant meetings or boards on behalf of the NCMHs. Thus, take the role of being the official voice of the NCMHs for topics such as development of EU policy.	
6. Publications and reports	Publication of white papers, policy reports, opinion papers on behalf of NCMHs.	

7. Add any other activity or service you think the EU network should provide to the NCMHs, please elaborate. [open text answer]

Annex II

In-depths interview semi-structured questions

Questions to start the conversation

1. Please tell us more about the mission of your institute/organisation
2. Could you please tell us more about the main activities performed within your NCMH and the resources to conduct those activities?
3. Do you have structural partnerships or alliances with other organisations to support these activities?
4. Could you give examples of in some successful initiatives or projects facilitated by the National Cancer Mission Hub that have had a significant impact on the cancer field in your country? What are the challenges you are facing in your NCMHs?

Questions on EU network barriers / facilitators

5. How do you see a European Network of NCMHs supporting you with facing these challenges? What are your expectations?
6. How crucial is political will and support from national governments in paving the way for a future EU network of National Cancer Mission Hubs?
7. Based on your experience, what would be the main facilitators or enablers in establishing an EU network of National Cancer Mission Hubs in the future?
8. What are obstacles or challenges that the EU network of NCMH could face?

Questions on collaboration with and within the EU network

9. How can collaboration and coordination within the EU network (ie. among different NCMHs) be fostered?
10. How can existing networks, organizations support the setup of a future EU network of National Cancer Mission Hubs?
11. In your opinion, how can the future EU network of National Cancer Mission Hubs foster collaboration and synergies with other international organizations or initiatives working towards similar objectives?
12. Do you think the future EU network of National Cancer Mission Hubs should address the needs and priorities of the different regions and countries within the EU?

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